

CHANGES IN ACCOUNTING ESTIMATES AND CORPORATE PROFITABILITY OF LISTED MANUFACTURING FIRMS IN NIGERIA

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Keywords: Accounting estimates, Operating Expense ratio, assets turnover ratio, return on equity, corporate profitability	Abstract: <i>The study aim to examine the effect of changes in accounting estimates on corporate profitability of manufacturing firms in Nigeria The study used secondary data from selected industrial businesses' financial filings from the Nigerian Stock Exchange (NSE), which spanned the years 2014 to 2023. The data was analysed using both descriptive statistics and Pearson Product Moment correlation analysis in SPSS. While operating expenditure ratio and return on equity appear to have no significant correlation, the data shows a considerable correlation between asset turnover ratio and return on equity. Accounting estimates has a significant influence on manufacturing firm profitability in Nigeria, according to the study. Asset turnover ratio and return on equity should be evaluated by manufacturing companies in order to improve their corporate profitability, according to the research.</i>
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INTRODUCTION

In today's corporate climate, accounting estimates and responsibility have taken on a significant role. A company's accounting estimates can be used by its managers, directors, shareholders, employees, and customers around the world to identify the firm's relative strengths and weaknesses, as well as steps the company may take in the future to capitalize on its strengths and fix its flaws. Zare and Shahsavari (2021) mention this fact. It is important to note that Appah (2022) describes accounting estimates as systems that perform the activities of data collection; processing; classifying; and

reporting financial occurrences in order to provide relevant information for score keeping, attention directing, and decision-making purposes; According to this definition, accounting estimates includes the components and aspects of an organization that offers information to users by processing financial events (Bodnar & Hopwood, 2020).

Some items recorded or recognized in the financial statements, usually prepared by the directors, cannot be measured with precision. They can only be estimated using managements' judgements and experience. Such financial statements items are commonly referred to as

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“accounting estimates”. Beechy (2005) opined that the majority of the transactions recorded and presented in the financial reports are mostly based on estimates. For instance, certain transactions such as: estimation of assets’ depreciation, measurement of impairment losses, making of warranty provisions, estimation of the closing inventories, estimation of assets’ economic lives, reserves recognition, determination of bad and doubtful debt provisions, estimation of employees’ retirement benefit obligation, valuation of intangible non-current assets, recognition of trade receivables, payables, etc. cannot be measured with precision (KPMG 2015). They are all measured and presented by way of accounting estimates. Raubenheimer (2012) argued that the use of accounting discretions in financial statements do not lead to precise amounts but, rather, figures based on presumptions, judgements, and guesses thoughtfully calculated by the preparers of the report. Chukwu (2006) summarized that when preparing and presenting financial statements, estimates are usually or frequently used and such events and their effects cannot be perceived with certainty; as almost all amounts are recognized and presented in financial statements by preparers today, reflect some form of estimates or the other. That is further buttressed by the International Accounting Standards Board (IASB, 2010) which opined that to a large extent, financial reports are prepared and presented based on certain accounting estimates, management judgements as well as models, as opposed to being an exact

representations of financial reality (IFRS Foundation; 2015). Accounting estimates, therefore, are those financial transactions or events that cannot be measured with precision or certainty during the preparation and presentation of financial statements. Arguably, we can trace most of the notable corporate accounting frauds and scandals in history to the misuse of accounting estimates or misuse of managements’ judgements, who sometimes creatively manipulate financial statements of their firms to make them appear appealing to the users (Nangih and Anichebe, 2021). For instance, the waste management scandal that took place in 1998 in Houston-Texas, the Tyco Scandal of 2002 involving New Jersey-based company managed by Dennis Kozlowski, and the Cadbury Nigeria Plc’s scandal of October 2006 were all traceable to the misuse of accounting estimates. It is for this reason that the financial regulators, notably, the Securities and Exchange Commission, the Financial Reporting Council of Nigeria, the International Accounting Standards Board, auditors and others, have always emphasized the importance of full disclosures; regarding critical accounting approximations and managements’ judgements done in the financial reports, since they significantly affect users’ perceptions and the way profits are determined.

As a result of the uncertainties inherent in business activities, many items in financial statements cannot be measured with precision but can only be estimated. Estimation involves judgments based on the latest available, reliable

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information. For example, estimates may be required of bad debts, inventory obsolescence, the fair value of financial assets or financial liabilities, the useful lives of, or expected pattern of consumption of the future economic benefits embodied in, depreciable assets; and Warranty obligations. The effect of a change in an accounting estimate, shall be recognized prospectively by including it in profit or loss in the period of the change, if the change affects that period only or the period of the change and future periods, if the change affects both. To the extent that a change in an accounting estimate gives rise to changes in assets and liabilities, or relates to an item of equity, it shall be recognized by adjusting the carrying amount of the related asset, liability or equity item in the period of the change.

The financial health of a company as a whole, capacity, and the ability to satisfy long-term financial obligations, operational expenditures, and agreements to supply services The term "corporate profitability" refers to what will happen in the near future. The degree to which financial goals are attained is referred to as corporate profitability in a broad sense (Amos & John, 2019). To review the firm's recent performance and plan for the future, financial managers rely on accountants' financial and accounting data. The goal is to get a suitable conclusion, to draw inferences about the firm's operating performance in relation to its financial situation and relevant future possibilities (Appah, 2022).

Statement of Problem

The accounting estimates provided by the firms are considered to be more relevant because it is not absolutely subjective. Again, it is also considered to be more realistic such as rate of return, current assets, inventory level, turnover, profit before tax and interest, marketability, etc which give a partial guarantee on the ability of an investors to invest and contribute to wealth maximization of the firms (Chandra, 2021). To make good judgments, you need accurate and up-to-date data. Due to a lack of accurate information, most businesses fail.

Efforts have been made by previous researchers to solve the problem associated with the misuse of accounting estimates by the preparers of financial statements. For instance, Lugovsky and Kuter (2020), Serdarevic (2011), Raubenheimer (2012), Belsoi et al (2017); all examined the subject matter of accounting estimates and how they affect financial statements prepared by firms. In Nigeria, Nnah (2017), Akenbor and Kiabel (2014), Ayunku and Eweke (2019), Ahmed et al (2014) as well as Anichebe and Nangih (2021) all maintained that accounting estimates had significant relationship with financial statements 'credibility or quality. However, I am not aware of any known study which examined the effect of changes in accounting estimates on the corporate profitability of manufacturing companies in Nigeria to the best of my knowledge. Consequently, an attempt to empirically examined the effect of these changes in accounting estimates on the corporate profitability of listed manufacturing companies

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in Nigeria. This study attempt to solve this problem by empirical estimation of the effects of changes in accounting estimates on corporate profitability of listed manufacturing firms, using return on equity, operating expenditure ratio and assets turnover ratio as proxies.

Conceptual Framework

This study uses Changes in Accounting Estimates as the independent variable with operating expenditure ratio and asset turnover ratio as proxies. The dependent variable is the corporate profitability of manufacturing firms with return on equity as proxy. These proxies are depicted in Fig. 1.1

Fig 1.1: Conceptual Framework of the Relationship between Changes in Accounting Estimates and Corporate Profitability of Manufacturing Firms in Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

The overall goal of this research was to examine the effect of changes in accounting estimates on corporate profitability of manufacturing firms in Nigeria. The specific objectives of the research are to:

i. Ascertain the relationship between operational expenditure ratio and return on equity of manufacturing firms in Nigeria.

ii. Determine the relationship between assets turnover ratio and return on equity of manufacturing firms in Nigeria.

Research Hypothesis

The following hypotheses are provided in the null form in order to answer the above-mentioned research questions.

HO₁: There is no significant relationship between operational expenditure ratio and return on equity of manufacturing firms in Nigeria.

HO₂: There is no significant relationship between asset turnover ratio and return on equity of manufacturing firms in Nigeria.

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REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Conceptual Review

Accounting Estimates

As defined by the American Accounting Association (AAA), accounting is the identification, measurement, and communication of economic information in order to enable informed judgements and choices by users of information. Accounting information is needed by all businesses, regardless of size, whether they are for profit or non-profit, according to Appah (2022). Accounting estimates are based on management judgements and assumptions. They are approximations of the amounts of business transactions for which there are no exact or precise means of measurements (Nnah, 2017). According to the International Auditing Standards Board (IASB 2009), accounting estimation involves management judgments and opinions based on availability of information during the preparation of financial statements. It involves making particular assumptions about matters that are quite uncertain at the time of estimation, as financial reporting frameworks may only provide basis or guide for management on how to determine point estimates where options exist.

Financial statements are the bedrock of financial communication, providing stakeholders with essential information about a company's performance and position. Within these documents, accounting estimates play a crucial role in reflecting management's expectations about future events that affect reported assets,

liabilities, income, and expenses. The importance of these estimates cannot be overstated as they have the power to significantly influence a company's financial health and investor perceptions. Changes in accounting estimates, therefore, are not just routine adjustments; they can have profound implications for a company's financial narrative. As businesses evolve and new information comes to light, accounting estimates may need to be revised to better reflect the company's current circumstances. These revisions can stem from new market conditions, changes in business operations, or the availability of more accurate data.

Indicators of Change

Indicators that a change in accounting estimates is warranted often emerge from the business environment or as a result of internal company developments. These indicators can include significant variations in market conditions, such as fluctuations in commodity prices that affect inventory valuations, or changes in technology that alter the useful life of fixed assets. Additionally, new legislation or regulations can necessitate adjustments to estimates related to tax liabilities, environmental provisions, or retirement benefit obligations. Internally, a company might identify changes in credit risk profiles of its customers, leading to an updated estimate of the allowance for doubtful accounts. The recognition of these indicators is a complex process, requiring a thorough analysis of both external and internal factors that could influence the estimates.

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Business is an economic entity that sells goods and services at a profit for its shareholders. One of the most important aspects of a company's survival is its capacity to generate enough revenue to attract and retain investment capital as well as its ability to pay its obligations on time. According to Benwini (2021), the accounting estimates in every company activity provides I operating operations, which include hiring employees, purchasing products or services, and paying taxes. Fundraising efforts (ii) are used to invest the money generated. A wide range of activities are involved in these transactions. It is necessary to engage in financing operations in order to secure business financing. Capital is obtained from owners and creditors; returns are paid to owners and creditors are repaid. Accounting estimates, according to Kashif (2018), is a collection of people, technology, policies, and processes that work together to gather data and turn it into valuable information. Management Information System (MIS) accounting information is viewed as a subsystem (MIS). "Accounting actually is an information system and if we be more precise accounting is practiced in the field of effective economic activity and consists of a major part of the information which is presented in the quantitative form" was stated in the AICPA (American Institute of Certified Public Accountants) was founded in 1966. Accounting is part of a company's overall information system. The term "AIS" can be used to describe financial transaction tracking systems. These systems integrate IT-industry methods, controls, and

accounting procedures to track transactions and give data for Organizational performance is financial records, including internal and external reporting, and trend analysis are all factors. They are based on information technology (IT) (Grande, 2021).

Operating expense ratio

Operating expense ratio is measured by comparing a company's total operating expenses (OER) and revenue. The operational ratio shows how successfully a company's management keeps costs down while boosting sales or revenue. A lower ratio shows that a corporation may earn more revenue while lowering its overall costs. Investment analysts can assess a company's success in a variety of ways. Because it focuses on basic firm activities, the operational in the field of performance evaluation, the ratio is one of the most often utilized techniques. It is frequently used, along with return on assets and return on equity, to evaluate a company's operational efficiency and effectiveness (Zuriekat et al., 2021). To identify patterns in operational efficiency or inefficiency, it is beneficial to maintain track of the operating ratio over time. An growing the operating ratio is a poor sign since it indicates that operational costs are increasing in comparison to sales or revenue. If the operating ratio is reducing, costs are decreasing, income is growing, or a combination of the two is increasing. If a company's operating ratio rises over time, it may be necessary to apply cost controls in order to boost margins.

Depreciation Estimates: Depreciation expense is an estimate of the amount of future

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economic benefits or service potential of tangible non-current assets that is expected to be consumed during the accounting period. It is done as a means of allocating the costs of tangible non-current assets to periods which the entity is likely to benefit from using such assets (the expected useful life). International Accounting Standard 16-Property, Plant and Equipment also provides for the reducing balance of depreciation estimation, as an alternative to the straight-line method. The reducing balance method of depreciation assumes that assets decline in value faster during the earlier years of acquisition and gradually slows down in depreciation with usage. However, both methods are based on estimates, and will produce differing results. Mert and Dil (2016) evaluated the influence of depreciation methods on performance measurement methods using energy firms listed on the Istanbul Stock Exchange between 2014-2015. The variables employed in the study were Economical Added Value (EVA) and Cash Flow Return on Investment (CFROI). Findings revealed that the differences in depreciation management of the energy industry firms had significant influence on performance indicators. Indrayani (2018) examined the analysis of non-current assets depreciation method on company profits. The study used the descriptive research design and also made use of descriptive statistics method of analysis. The variables for the study were straight line method, double declining method and profit for the year. It was concluded that the depreciation method and policy had significant effect on the company profit. The amount

charged as depreciation impacts on the profitability as well as the value of the firm, as the higher the depreciation charge, the lower the profitability and vice versa.

Closing Inventory Estimates: Inventory constitutes a reasonable proportion of a firm's total current asset. According to Milicevic, Davidovic and Stefanovic (2010), they form part of the current assets (which are assets that can be converted to cash in not more than one accounting year). IASB (2011) provides that abnormal costs and costs that represent waste should be excluded from when measuring the initial cost of inventories. Other costs that the standard excludes for the initial costs of inventory are: storage costs, administrative costs which are not part of the expenditure that is used to bring the inventories to their right location and condition, as well as selling and distribution costs. One basic provision of the standard when trying to recognize the closing value of inventory is that a comparison should be made between the costs and the inventories' net realizable value. By implication, all amounts recognized as closing inventories in financial statements are estimated; using either the costs or net realizable value. Koumanakos (2008) who examined the effect of inventory management on financial performance of selected firms concluded that a profitability is significantly and negatively influenced by the amount of closing inventory. He opined that the higher the value of closing inventory the lower the profit margin of firms.

Account Receivable Estimates: Accounts receivables are amounts of sales generated from

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the ordinary course of business but are not yet received. It refers to money which accrued to the firm from credit sales (Longe and Kareem 2012). Trade receivables are recognized initially at fair value and subsequently measured at amortized costs using the effective interest method less provisions for impairment. A provision for bad and doubtful debt for trade receivables is usually made if there is material evidence that based on past experiences that the firm will find it difficult collect all the amounts due from customers. This make the amount usually recognized to be estimated. Ramana, Ramakrishnaiah and Chengalrayulu (2013) studied the impact of receivables management on the working capital and profitability of listed cement companies in India. Ramana et al. (2014) found that selected companies in the cement industry were efficient in managing their trade receivables and this translated into lower collection period. The study revealed that efficient receivables management had a positive influence on both working capital and profitability.

Asset turnover ratio

The asset turnover ratio is calculated by comparing a firm's assets to its sales or revenues in order to estimate the profitability of the company. Known as the asset turnover ratio, it is a method of determining a company's capacity to convert assets into earnings (ATR). When a company's ability to generate income from its assets is measured, it is referred to as its asset turnover ratio. The asset turnover ratio will increase in direct proportion to the efficiency of the organization. If the firm's asset turnover ratio

is low, it indicates that the company is not adequately utilizing its assets to create money (Lin & Liu, 2019). The asset turnover ratio is typically calculated only once a year in the majority of circumstances. In addition, because a greater asset turnover ratio suggests that more money is being generated by a fixed number of assets, it is an indicator of a company's performance. Some sectors have greater asset turnover ratios than others, and the ratios vary depending on the industry. Asset turnover ratios are the greatest in the retail and consumer staples industries, for example, because of their tiny asset bases and large sales volumes. Large asset bases and minimal asset turnover are characteristic of utilities and real estate enterprises, on the other hand.

Property, plant and equipment Estimates:

Property, plant and equipment are tangible assets such as plant and machinery, motor vehicles, freehold and lease hold land and buildings, furniture & fittings under the control of an entity for production or supply of goods or services or for administrative purposes. The management of these resources underpins the continued viability of a business and therefore represents a key feature of business prosperity (Chukwu; 2006). Property plant and equipment costs are included in the financial statements as an asset; if the costs can be measured reliably and it is probable that the assets will generate future economic benefits for the entity. Property plant and equipment are carried at costs or revalued amounts in the financial statements depending on the accounting policy of the entity

and the model being used. These estimations are mostly based on the expertise and the information available at the disposal of staff who have good knowledge on how the asset functions and experience with similar assets. Such estimates could be reviewed if there are new information available to management on the state of the assets or its physical wear and tear (Bhattacharyya; 2011). This goes to show that all carrying amounts of property plant and equipment are estimated by management.

Intangible Non-Current Assets Estimates:

Intangible assets are assets that do not have visible form. Since they do not possess any physical or financial embodiment; they are sometimes called knowledge assets. According to International Accounting Standard (IAS 38), these assets are identifiable non-monetary assets that do not have physical form. Examples of intangibles are development costs, goodwill, trademarks, licenses, franchises, etc. Intangibles assets amounts are usually measured, recognized and presented in financial statements using reliable estimates, as they cannot be measured with precision. IAS 38 prescribes the required treatment of intangibles assets. The standard specifies that an intangible asset should be recorded in the financial statement only when it is relatively certain that future economic benefits are expected from the use of such assets will flow to the entity and where the costs of the asset can be measured with a certain level of reliability. It specifies that when assets meet that recognition criteria, the initial measurement of the asset should be at costs. However, it allows entities to

choose either the cost model or the revaluation model during subsequent recognition. According to Chukwu (2006), under the cost model, the intangible asset should be carried at costs after the deduction of accumulated amortization and accumulated impairment losses. The revaluation model, on the other hand, requires that an asset be recognized at its restated or revalued amount. This means that the asset will be carried at its estimated value at the date of revaluation minus any subsequent accumulated amortization and any subsequent accumulated impairment losses. By implication, the amounts usually shown for intangible assets are estimates, as they are prone to management judgements and approximations.

Corporate Profitability

Corporate profitability refers to financial health of an organization, capacity and willingness to meet long-term financial obligations, and commitment to provide services in the near future (Weber, 2020). The act of engaging in financial activities is referred to as corporate profitability. How successfully financial goals are being reached or have been accomplished is referred to as "corporate profitability." What it's all about is the process of assigning an economic value to a company's policies and actions. Corporate profitability refers to a company's ability to meet its financial goals. Both investor returns and accounting returns are useful metrics for measuring a company's financial health. However, the accounting return investigates how diverse management techniques affect the firm's profitability

(Ofogebu, 2019). According to Farah et al. (2022), a company's financial health throughout time is measured by its corporate profitability. Management of the company's current and non-current assets, finance, equity, revenues, and costs is a financial activity that aims to improve a company's profitability and shareholder value. With this data, shareholders and other interested parties may make well-informed investment choices. Use it to compare industries as a whole, or to compare the results of businesses in the same industry.

Return on Equity

The return on equity (ROE) ratio is calculated by dividing net income by the total amount of equity held by shareholders. The term "return on net assets" refers to the fact that shareholders' equity equals the sum of the company's assets less its debt (RONA). The return on investment (ROI) gauges how well a company's management utilizes its assets to generate profits. ROE is the most widely used metric of profitability when comparing the performance of companies in the same industry (Besely, 2006). One of the most commonly used metrics to measure profitability is the return on equity (ROE). The greater the values, the better the company's capacity to produce money from new investments. A good beginning points for analyzing investors is to compare the return on rights of shareholders of different companies and to evaluate the evolution in the rules of participation over time. However, depending solely on the rights of shareholders and making investment decisions is not a secure strategy. For example, if a company

uses debt financing to lower its capital, the return on equity will rise even though the company's income remains unchanged (Gitman and Zutter, 2021).

Firm Size: The size of a firm cannot be overruled when it comes to the determination of corporate profitability. Larger firms are likely to be more profitable than smaller firms due to economies of scale and other factors. Most companies are intent to expand the size of their business operation for them to grow either in revenue, number of employees, or size of facilities (Pervan and Visic, 2012). The firm size is measured by different authors in different ways such as total asset, turnover, and sometimes the market capitalization. According to Aulia and Agustina (2015) argued that firm size is a scale that depicts a company classified as either large or small. According to Kartikasari and Merianti (2016), firm size can be measured by the natural logarithm of total assets or natural logarithm of total sales. In this study, we used natural logarithm of total assets, as a measure of firm size.

Theoretical Review

Agency Theory

According to Meckling and Jensen (1976), agency relationship contract exists between one or more persons-the principal and another person (agent) to perform some service on their behalf, which involves delegating some decision-making authority to the agent. Agency theory evolution also owes much to the corporate governance literature, which analyzes the problem of separation of ownership and control

(Grabbling *et al.*, 2019). In the manufacturing industry, an changes in accounting estimate plays an important role in reducing both operational expenses and capital cost by empirically confirming the validity of financial statements and agency problems. The principal-agent conflict is illustrated in agency theory, where the principal (owner) lacks reasons to believe their agents (managers) due to information asymmetries and contradictory motives (Hillebrandt, 2018). Jensen and Meckling (1976), states that in agency theory, agents have more information than principals and this information asymmetry adversely affects the principals' ability to monitor whether or not their interests are being properly served by the agents. The agency theory proposes that a firm's main objective is to maximize the shareholder's wealth. The theory states that the organization consists of principals who are the owners of the economic resources and the agents who are the managers of the principal's resources. One objection to agency theory is that it relies on an assumption of self-interested agents who seek to maximize personal economic wealth. The agency theory helps the study to explain the use of changes in accounting estimates in organizations but can also help explain some of the characteristics of the accounting estimates and the scope of its changes, such as operational expenses versus performance within the organization.

The principals believe that the agents are not to be trusted because they may be more interested in enriching themselves at the expense of their principals. To ensure managers maximize owner's wealth rather than enrich themselves, there is an agency cost. There are basically three types of agency costs:

- Expenditure to monitor managerial activities e.g. audit costs.
- Expenditure to structure the organization in a way to limit managerial behaviour.
- Opportunity costs incurred when owners impose restrictions e.g. limit the ability of managers to take action that advance owner's wealth.

The principal-agent relationship is more hierarchical and power-driven than a contractual relationship. There is a greater latitude for principal to reward, punish and control agents. There are usually changes in accounting estimates designed to add value and improve an organizations operation.

Empirical Review

Bawa, Asamoah and Kissi (2022) studied the influence of inventory management on firm performance of quoted manufacturing companies in Ghana. Using a cross sectional secondary data, the sample was 140 firm-year observations drawn from 14 listed manufacturing firms listed on the Ghana Stock Exchange (GSE) for a 10-year period, 2012-2021. Data collected were tested using Pearson correlation and multiple regression analysis. The empirical findings revealed that inventory

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management had no effect on firm's performance. The result showed that the independent variable was insignificantly related to dependent variable for the period. Indrayani (2018) examined the analysis of fixed assets depreciation method on company profits in Indonesia. The study used the descriptive research design and also made use of descriptive statistics method of analysis. The variables for the study were straight line method, double declining method and profit for the year. It was concluded that the depreciation method and policy had significant effect on the company profit.

Akwu, Ofoegbu and Okafor (2022) also investigated the effect of fair value measurement and depreciation on performance of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria. Using depreciation amount, inflation rate and IFRS as independent variables and the reported profit as proxy for the dependent variable, the regression results showed that IFRS had positive and no significant effect on depreciation and also insignificant effect on reported profit of the companies in Nigeria.

Chukwu and Egbuhuzor (2022) examined the effect of non-current assets (property plant and equipment) on the corporate performance of manufacturing firms in Nigeria. The study used financial statement data from ten manufacturing companies listed on the stock exchange, and measured corporate performance using return on assets and return on equity. Results from multiple regression analysis revealed that a significant and positive relationship exist between return on assets and plant & machinery.

However, the relationship between return on assets and land & buildings was negative. The study therefore came to a conclusion that tangible noncurrent assets investments affects the profitability of firms.

Belsoi, Gathii and Phillip (2021) assessed the influence of estimates on firm performance of Microfinance firms in Kenya. The study population was ninety-three (93) persons in three different strata (account officers, internal auditors and management) of the 14 microfinance institutions. Their findings revealed that there exists positive, but very significant relationship exist between independent variable (assets estimation) and financial performance of microfinance institutions. It also discovered a significant negative association exist between the estimation of an asset's useful life and financial performance. Ayunku and Eweke (2017) assessed the relationship between accounting estimates and financial reporting quality of banks in Nigeria, employing data from annual reports of seventeen (17) quoted money deposit banks spanning the period 2008 – 2017. Based on the results of the OLS regression, it was discovered that provisions for bad debt and depreciation, which were used as proxies for accounting estimates had a significant relation with financial reporting quality (which was measured using discretionary accruals accounting). The study concluded that there is need for accounting harmonization by all preparers of financial statements globally to ensure infirmity in the way estimates are made in

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financial statements; as this will enhanced financial reporting quality.

Zhang (2021) investigated the nexus between degree of intangibles and firm profitability. The study employed intangible assets and return on assets as variables for study. Using 17 listed telecommunication companies' financial statements in China between 2015 to 2019, the study gave empirical evidence that intangible assets had positive and significant relationship with firms' financial performance, proxied by Return on Assets (ROA).

Wanyoike, (2021) researched on the impact of accounts receivable management on financial performance of manufacturing firms in Kenya. They administered questionnaire on a sample of 50 manufacturing companies. Data from secondary sources was also sourced from the firms' annual audited financial accounts. From the results of the analysis done, it was discovered that there existed a positive relationship between accounts receivable and financial performance of listed firms in Kenya.

Lubyanaya, Izmailov, Nikulina and Shaposhnikov (2021) assessed the impact of non-current assets on profits measurements as well as and asset management efficiency of listed firms in Russia. Its main aim was to investigate and identify the impact of estimates and valuation in accounting for non-current fixed assets. The study used the deductive methodology as well as the quantitative analysis method. The findings revealed that differences in the measurement of accounting figures under IFRS directly affected the numerator, their

denominator, or both. It concludes that non-current assets had effect on profitability.

Gorondutse, Ali and Ali (2021) investigates the effect of trade receivables and inventory management on SMEs profitability in Malaysia. A total of 66 sample of SMEs in the manufacturing sector were used for the study between 2015-2019. OLS regression was used to estimate the relationship between independent variable and the dependent variable. The findings showed that days account receivable and inventory turnover in days were negatively related to SME profitability measured using return on assets (ROA), return on equity (ROE) and net operating profit (NOP). This result simply implies that profitability of SMEs is dependent or influenced by effective of working capital management.

Mwangi (2021) sought to study influence of inventory management on firm's profitability and operating cash flows using Kenya Breweries companies. The study made use of a descriptive research design. The study population was six Kenya Breweries carried out by way of census. Data collected between 2011-2020 was analyzed using ordinary least squares regression method. The study found a significant and strong relationship between the management of inventory and the operating cash flows. It also concluded that inventory management significantly affects firm profitability and operating cash flows.

Anichebe and Nangih (2021) assessed the effects of accounting estimates on information misstatements of financial reports of Small and

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Medium Enterprises in Nigeria. The study employed survey design. They examined the impacts of depreciation estimates, impairment loss, inventory estimates, goodwill estimates and estimated useful life of assets on financial reports. The findings revealed that wrong estimates may lead to, but are not the only cause of misstatements in financial reports.

Prempeh (2020), in his study evaluated the effect of efficient inventory management on profitability of selected manufacturing companies in Ghana. Data was collected and analyzed between 2005 to 2019 from the annual reports of only manufacturing firms that were listed on the quoted on the Ghana Stock Exchange. The method of analysis employed in the study was Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression model. Findings of the study revealed that raw materials inventory management had significant and positive impacts on profitability of manufacturing firms in Ghana.

Gamayuni (2020) examined the effect of intangible assets, financial performance and financial policies on firm value of Indonesian companies. Empirically, the study sought to know the relationship between intangible assets, financial policies, and financial performance companies in Indonesia. Path analysis was adopted to ascertain the relationship between the variables between 2011 to 2019. This study found that Intangible assets, financial policies, financial performance had significant influence on firm value simultaneously. It was also found that intangible assets had no significant effect to financial policies, but had positive and

significant relationship with financial performance measured by ROA and firm value. Debt policies and ROA influenced firm value positively and also significantly.

Olaoye and Adeniyi (2020) examined the influence of accounting manipulations on the financial performance of selected listed firms in Nigeria. They specifically examined the causes of accounting discretions and also to find out if there were substantial influence of accounting manipulations on financial performance of firms in Nigeria. The study adopted a descriptive research design using survey for collection of data. Descriptive statistical tools and Ordinary Least Squares regression were employed to analyze data. Findings revealed that accounting manipulations negatively influence performance of corporate firms sampled. The study recommended that stakeholders should put in place effective policies and stringent penalty for violators to check the incidences of accounting manipulations among Nigerian firms.

Lugovsky and Kuter (2020) investigated the effect of accounting policies and accounting estimates and its role in the preparation of fair financial statements in digital economy in Russia. The study made use of the exploratory research design and considered the main problems and limitations of the reliable preparation and presentation of reporting financial information. The study concluded that the degree or choice of freedom provided by standard setters to preparers has a serious influence on the reporting data presented to the users by them. It also added that the reliability of

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financial reports is influenced by many other factors including but not limited to the choice of accounting, depreciation policies, legality of the transaction and changes in accounting estimates. Abubakar and Olowe (2019) looked at the effect of trade receivables on firm performance of selected listed firms in Nigeria. The population consists of ten (10) firms listed on the Nigerian stock exchange from 2012 to 2018 selected using purposive sampling technique. The study employed the multiple regressions method to test the formulated hypotheses. The dimensions for accounts receivable were accounts receivable ratio, debt ratio and revenue growth whereas firm performance was measured using return on equity. The result of the analysis showed that accounts receivable ratio, debt ratio and revenue growth had a positive significant influence on firm performance.

Ganyam and Ivungu (2019) assessed the effect of accounting information system on financial performance of firms. Specifically, the study aimed at reviewing the conceptual and theoretical issues on the subject area of accounting information system and relating it to financial performance of firms. Results from the review showed that accounting information had effect on financial performance. The study also found out that most of the prior works employed the survey research design to examine the relationships while majority of the studies were carried out in advanced economies and not in less developed economies like Nigeria.

Erika et al. (2019) looked at the value of financial accounting data in corporate management. The

study used a survey research technique, with questionnaire data serving as the major source of information. The data was analyzed using the Spearman rank correlation coefficient. Financial accounting notion that financial accounting is utilized as information for corporate decision making and decision is shown to have a substantial low positive relationship, according to the study's findings.

Anastasia, Michael and Innocent (2019) examined accounts receivable management and corporate performance of companies in the food & beverage industry in Nigeria. The independent variables used for the study were accounts receivable, debt and sales growth. Secondary sources of data were used from 2009-2018. Multiple regression was used analyze the test of hypotheses. The findings of the study revealed that accounts receivable had negative but insignificant relationship with profitability, while debt and sales growth had positive and insignificant relationship with profitability of food and beverages manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

Okwo, Ugwunta and Nweze (2019) assessed the impact of a company's investment in noncurrent assets on its operating profit margin. The study used four companies in the Nigerian brewery sector for the period 2002 -2018. Employing regression statistical method to ascertain the relationship between the independent and dependent variables, the study found out that though the relationship was positive, but the result was not statistically significant. Hence, the result did not suggest a strong positive impact of

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investment in non-current assets on the operating profit of brewery firms in Nigeria.

Wale and Sunday (2018) investigated the Nigerian industrial enterprises' profitability is negatively impacted by financial statement fraud. The goal of this research was to see how faulty asset valuation and incorrect expense recognition influenced the company's total profitability (ROA). Listed On the Nigerian Stock Exchange, there are food and beverage firms form the study's population. The financial records of the selected firms were used in a descriptive research technique. The STATA II econometric approach was used to analyze the data, and several statistical procedures. The parameters were validated using t-tests, coefficients of determination (R²), F-statistics, and Wald chi-square at a 5% level of significance. The outcomes of the study show that financial statement fraud has a major impact on Nigerian manufacturing industry profitability. For the sake of Nigeria's manufacturing industry, it was advised that manufacturing enterprises implement an efficient internal control system in order to prevent financial statement fraud.

Akhor and Jafaru (2015), employ ratio analysis to assess the performance of a group of publicly traded companies from 2009 to 2013. An ordinary least square regression approach was used in conjunction with a descriptive statistic, Pearson correlation matrix, and Pearson correlation matrix. Using basic regression approaches, the empirical data demonstrated that the liquidity ratio had a negative and substantial influence on business performance.

There is little influence on a company's financial outcomes from the leverage ratio and the market ratio. The profitability ratio has a significant positive impact on the evaluation of a company's performance. According to the study results, management and policyholders see liquidity and profitability ratios as actual key performance indicators, as well as paying attention to additional in future empirical investigation, factors that may aid performance evaluation using ratio analysis.

Gap

Based on the results of a scientific study, various research examining the interplay between the two accounting estimates and corporate profitability of manufacturing firms. As a result of the preceding evaluation of pertinent literature, it is clear that research has been conducted in the field of accounting estimates and performance, but not in a comprehensive manner. To my knowledge, none of the earlier research examined chosen manufacturing firms in Nigeria; instead, they focused on other industries. A gap in the literature on accounting estimates and corporate profitability in Nigerian manufacturing firms will be filled by this study.

3. METHODOLOGY

This study adopted the *ex-post facto* research designs in a bid to examine the effect of changes in accounting estimates on corporate profitability of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria. The study's target population was manufacturing firms in Nigeria, however the accessible population comprised of twenty (20) manufacturing firms listed on the Nigerian

Exchange Group as at December 31st 2023, a sample size of five (5) firms were used. These were chosen based on the availability of comprehensive financial reports online for the period covered (2014-2023). The period reflects the post-IFRS adoption in Nigeria, when all the financial statements under consideration were prepared based on a unified and globally acceptable accounting standard. The nature of

the data was panel data. The Statistical Package for Social Science was used to perform descriptive statistics and correlation analyses in this study (SPSS). Pearson's Product Moment Correlation Coefficient was used to determine the relationship between the variables and to test the null hypotheses at the 0.05 level of significance.

ANALYSIS OF THE RESULT

Table 1 Statistics of descriptive

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	Skewness		Kurtosis	
	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic	Std. Error
OPEXPR	50	0.03	0.28	0.1576	0.08574	-0.303	0.472	-1.390	0.918
ASSTURNR	50	0.18	1.72	1.0903	0.35235	-0.509	0.472	0.857	0.918
ROE	50	0.01	1.00	0.3202	0.29136	0.967	0.472	-0.283	0.918
Valid N (listwise)	50								

Source: Researcher's Computation from data collected using SPSS (Version 20)

As seen in this table-1, all variables exhibit a positive growth rate between their lowest and highest statistical values. The asset turnover ratio jumps from 0.18 to 1.72, operating expenses jump from 0.03, and return on equity jumps from 0.01 to 1.0. The results also reveal that the mean, standard deviation, skewness, and kurtosis all have a very consistent level of consistency. According to the numerous data, the variables have a diverse distribution. The

skewness and kurtosis statistics are important for determining the symmetry of various data series' probability distributions, as well as the thickness of their tails. Operating expenses ratio and assets turnover ratio are negatively skewed showing that they have a short right tail. In addition, the results show that the operating expense ratio and the return on equity are A positive asset turnover ratio and a negative kurtosis indicate that the distribution is flat, whereas kurtosis statistics indicate that the distribution is less flat than the normal curve.

Table 2: Correlations Coefficient of Hypothesis one

		OPEXPR	ROE
OPEXPR	Pearson Correlation	1	0.282
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.182
	N	24	24
ROE	Pearson Correlation	0.282	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.182	
	N	24	24

Source: Researcher's Computation using SPSS (Version 20)

Note: The operational expenditure ratio and the return on equity of manufacturing company's corporate profitability have no link at all

Table 2 shows the result of Pearson correlation coefficient of relationship between operating expenses ratio (accounting estimates) and manufacturing firms return on equity (corporate profitability) in Nigeria. With a P-value of 0.182,

which is larger than the statistically significant level of 0.05, the table above reveals a correlation coefficient of 0.282, showing a slight positive relationship between operational expenses ratio and return on equity. As a result, we reject the alternate and adopt the null hypothesis, accordingly there is no significant relationship between operating expenditure ratio and corporate profitability of listed manufacturing firm's return on equity.

Table 3: Correlation Coefficient of Hypothesis Two

		ASSTURNR	ROE
ASSTURNR	Pearson Correlation	1	0.681**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.000
	N	24	24
ROE	Pearson Correlation	0.681**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	
	N	24	24

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2tailed).

Source: Researcher's Computation using SPSS (Version 20)

Note: The corporate profitability of manufacturing companies has no meaningful

correlation with the asset turnover ratio and the return on equity.

Table 3 illustrates the Pearson correlation coefficient of the relationship between the asset's turnover ratio (accounting estimates) and the

return on equity (corporate profitability) of Nigerian manufacturing firms. It's clear that assets turnover ratio and return on equity are linked by a correlation coefficient of 0.681, which has a p-value of 0.000, substantially lower than the usual 0.01 and 0.05 criteria of significance. As a result, Nigerian manufacturing firms financial results are strongly linked to their assets turnover ratio, which we reject as a null hypothesis and favor as an alternate hypothesis.

Discussion of Findings

According to a correlation coefficient of 0.282 and a P-value of 0.182, the OER and ROE of Nigerian manufacturing firms have no meaningful link. This finding is in line with that of Akho and Jafacu (2015), who found a significant link between operating expenditure ratio (OER) and return on equity (ROE) in manufacturing firms in Nigeria. Hypothesis two was tested and the correlation coefficient of 0.681 was arrived at and P-value of 0.000 at 0.01 and 0.05 level of significant. It implied a significant relationship. As a result, the null hypothesis is rejected to say there is significant relationship between the assets turnover ratio (ATR) and the return on equity (ROE) in

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Nigerian manufacturing firms. This conclusion is consistent with Lin and Liu (2015), who discovered that ATR and ROE have a link.

CONCLUSIONS

AND

RECOMMENDATIONS

This study had two goals, both of which were met. The study found that changes in accounting estimates had somewhat significant effect on Nigerian manufacturers' corporate profitability is based on empirical facts shown above. As a result, manufacturing companies may utilize the assets turnover ratio of financial data to forecast the rise of return on equity in their corporate profitability. The following suggestions are made based on the study's findings:

1. Manufacturing firms should appraise assets turnover assets ratio and return on equity in order to improve on their corporate profitability.
2. To improve efficiency and effectiveness in performance, personnel should be taught how to use realistic changes in accounting estimates.
3. Accounting department workers should be offered seminars/training to enable them to specialize further in the subject of accounting standards and estimates

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